

Structure, bonding and superalkali behaviour of organo-Zintl clusters X_7Me_4 ($X = As, Sb$ and Bi)

G. Naresh Reddy^a, Aritra Mukhopadhyay^a, Rakesh Parida^a, Gourisankar Roymahapatra^b and Santanab Giri^{*a}

^aTheoretical Chemistry Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, National Institute of Technology, Rourkela-769 008, Odisha, India

^bDepartment of Applied Sciences, Haldia Institute of Technology, Haldia-721 657, West Bengal, India

E-mail: giris@nitrkl.ac.in

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Zintl ions are a special class of multianionic species consists of group 13, 14 and 15 elements in the periodic table. The group 15 elements arsenic (As), antimony (Sb), and bismuth (Bi) based organo-Zintl clusters have been designed with ligand H and methyl (Me). First principle calculation shows that, the organo-Zintl complex $X_7(Me)_4$ ($X = As, Sb$ and Bi) shows superalkali nature with less adiabatic ionization energy (AIE) values as compared with alkali metal ionization energies. Among the group 15 Zintl ions X_7^{3-} ($X = As, Sb$ and Bi), As_7^{3-} is found to be the best candidate in making superalkali. H is not suitable as compare to Me group for making superalkali complex. The 2c-2e, density of states and partial density of states lend additional information on the structure and bonding of these complexes.

Keywords: Superalkali, Zintl ion, DFT, organo-Zintl cluster, adiabatic ionization energies.

Introduction

Atomic cluster can be considered as an assembly of several atoms¹ their properties are depending not only on the size, but also the arrangement of the atoms. Due to their versatile properties, the cluster science area has expanded in several fields. It is assumed that, the assemble of clusters lead to bulk material and they retain their properties inside the bulk. This leads to the formation of materials with tailored properties. During the formation of the cluster, the metal atoms try to organize to gain stability either as cation or anion. Two specific sets of cluster that fit into these groups are superalkali²⁻⁴ and superhalogens⁵⁻⁸ respectively. For the first time Gutsev and Boldyrev coined the word superalkali⁹⁻¹¹, they found that if a cluster has the formula $M_{k+1}L$, where M is the alkali atom and L is the electronegative element with valence k, then they behave like superalkali, which have lower ionization energy than alkali metals like Li, Na, K, ... etc. Typical example of superalkali complexes are, Li_2F , Li_3O , Li_4N , ... etc.¹². Here F, O and N have valences 1, 2 and 3 respectively. So to attain stable electronic configuration, they will eject one electron to form cationic complex. In this way one can design molecules with low ionization energy (IE) even lower than traditional alkali atom Li, Na, K, ... etc. Apart from

this traditional formula, there are different kinds of superalkalis reported in the literature which not necessarily obey this formula. Some of them are binuclear, non metallic, polynuclear, aromatic, aromatic heterocyclic superalkalis... etc.¹³⁻¹⁸. On the other hand superhalogens are the complexes having high electron affinity (EA) than chlorine (Cl) (3.6 eV). They also have the general formula MX_{n+1} . Here, M is a metal atom, X is a halogen atom, and n is the maximum valence of the metal atom. One typical example is BF_4 where B is trivalent. To accommodate extra F, BF_4 takes an extra electron. This results high EA 6.86 eV. It has been found that there are several systems that have high EA but, they do not obey the general formula given by Gutsev and Boldyrev. In spite of several examples, superalkali or superhalogen having Zintl core is very less. Recently Giri *et al.*¹⁹ designed a new class of superalkali based on Zintl ion P_7^{3-} as core and alkyl groups as ligand. They found that $P_7(C(CH_3)_3)_4$ complex has the ionization energy less than K and close to Cs. Zintl ions²⁰⁻²⁶ are a special kind of atomic clusters, commonly found in multi anionic species and they mostly belong to group 13, 14 and 15 elements. Their stability can be explained either by Zintl-Klemm concept, Octet rule, Jellium shell closing model or Wade-Mingos rule²⁷⁻³⁰. Nowadays, the concept of Zintl ion

has been extended to all metal complexes. Jena *et al.*³¹ showed that it is possible to extend the idea of Zintl concept and they proposed to have all metal Zintl ions that obey the 18 electron rule. In a recent publication Reddy *et al.*³² also demonstrated that it is also possible to have magnetic all metal Zintl ions and Zintl phase. It has been found that most of the group 15 elements form Zintl ion and they have the formula as X_7^{3-} ($X = \text{As, Sb and Bi}$). They have nortricyclane structure with C_{3v} symmetry. Their stability can be explained by using Octet rule. For the group 15 Zintl ions, X_7^{3-} ($X = \text{As, Sb and Bi}$), X_7 have 35 valence electrons. To gain the stability they required 3 extra electrons, thus fulfill the Octet rule. As mentioned earlier, P_7^{3-} makes superalkali complexes with different alkyl groups, we wanted to investigate two problems. First whether all the elements of group 15 can have similar kind of properties of making superalkali complexes and second is there any change in IE going down the group. It is well known fact that the IE decreases down the group, so it is expected that we can have superalkali complexes with other elements of group 15 with lower IE when they form complex with alkyl group. This is exactly what we wanted to investigate in this manuscript. Two ligands, H and Me have been used to form different Zintl complexes with As_7^{3-} , Sb_7^{3-} , and Bi_7^{3-} . The computational details are discussed in Section 2. Results and discussion and Conclusion are given in Section 3 and 4 respectively.

Computational details:

We have optimized all the X_7^{3-} ($X = \text{As, Sb and Bi}$) geometries using B3LYP/def2-TZVPP³³⁻³⁵ level of theory. For Sb and Bi we have incorporated pseudopotential in our calculation. Same level of theory and basis set is used to get all possible ground state geometries for all neutral X_7H_4 ($X = \text{As, Sb and Bi}$) and $X_7(\text{Me})_4$ ($X = \text{As, Sb and Bi}$) complexes. All possible combinations of X_7H_4 ($X = \text{As, Sb and Bi}$) and

$X_7(\text{Me})_4$ ($X = \text{As, Sb and Bi}$) keeping the nortricyclane geometry intact have been tried and optimized to get the lowest energy isomer. Moreover, depending on the ligand orientation of the ligands in the upper triangle part of X_7^{3-} , two types of isomers *cis* and *trans* are possible. Both the isomers of these complexes are also optimized to get the most stable isomer. All optimizations have been performed without employing any symmetry constrains. Vibration frequency calculations at the same level of theory were carried out to ensure that all the geometries are on the local minimum on their respective potential energy surface. To get the adiabatic ionization energy (AIE) of all studied complexes we have also optimized the cationic part using B3LYP/def2-TZVPP level of theory. To get more accurate AIE values, we have recalculated the AIE in MP2 level of theory with same basis set used in B3LYP calculation. To determine the bonding features and charge density on each atom of the designed complexes, we have performed natural bond orbital (NBO)³⁶ analysis. A 2c-2e bond analysis using adaptive natural density partitioning (AdNDP) technique has been performed to know the s electron sharing of the ligands for the formation of the complexes. All the calculations were performed in the Gaussian 09 program³⁷ and Multiwfn software³⁸. The projected density of states (PDOS) calculations were carried out by using GaussSum software³⁹.

Results and discussion

The optimized geometry of all X_7^{3-} ($X = \text{As, Sb and Bi}$) Zintl ions are given in Fig. 1. We have found that all the X_7^{3-} geometries are nortricyclane in nature with point group C_{3v} . All the structures are well matched with the experimentally found geometries. The stability of all X_7^{3-} Zintl ions can be explained by Octet rule as all neutral X_7 have 35 valence electrons. To gain stability they will take extra 3 electrons to have 38 electronic systems.

Fig. 1. Optimized geometries of X_7^{3-} ($X = \text{As, Sb and Bi}$) Zintl ions.

As mentioned earlier, our main aim is to see whether all the group 15 elements can make superalkali complexes, we have taken two ligands, H and Me to make Zintl cluster X_7R_4 ($E = As, Sb, Bi$; $R = H, Me$). For all the cases we have taken both *cis* and *trans* isomers in order to make sure that which isomer is stable.

$[X_7R_4]$ ($X = As, Sb, Bi$ and $R = H, Me$) complexes:

(a) $[As_7R_4]$ ($R = H, Me$) complexes:

At first we start our discussion with $[As_7R_4]$ ($R = H, Me$) complexes. To find all possible isomers of these complexes we have performed NBO charge analysis on X_7^{3-} ($X = As, Sb$ and Bi). From the NBO analysis, it has been found that three different charges are present in X_7^{3-} ($X = As, Sb$ and Bi). The upper triangle, lower triangle and capped one. Experimentally it has been found that the upper triangle positions are suitable for ligand substitution. Now depending on the fourth position we have chosen two isomers. One is in capped and another is in lower triangle position. The optimized Cartesian coordinates of all the studied complexes are given in Supporting Information S1-12. The optimized geometries of all isomers of $[As_7H_4]$ with their *cis* and *trans* geometries and their energies are given in Supporting Information S13 and the optimized geometries of all the isomers of $[As_7Me_4]$ with relative energies are shown in Fig. 2.

From Fig. 2, it is evident that for *cis* neutral $[As_7Me_4]$ isomer, isomer 2 is more stable than isomer 1 by 0.36 eV.

The same is true for *trans* neutral isomer. Here also isomer 2 is more stable than isomer 1 by 0.99 eV. But the situation is reversed when we have obtained its cationic counterpart to calculate the adiabatic ionization energy (AIE). In cation geometries, we have observed that for cation isomers, the isomer 1 is more stable than isomers 2 in both *cis* and *trans* form. All the calculated AIE's of $[As_7R_4]$ ($R = H, Me$) complexes are given in Table 1. From the values given in Table 1 it is evident that, except H complex, all the Me complexes show superalkali behaviour. The values obtained from B3LYP level of theory further decrease when MP2 calculation has been performed.

After having the idea that, these clusters can be treated

Table 1. Calculated adiabatic ionization energies of As_7R_4 ($R = H$ and Me) complexes at B3LYP and MP2 level of theories by using Def2-TZVPP basis set

Complexes	Adiabatic ionization energies (AIE's)	
	B3LYP/Def2-TZVPP	B3LYP/Def2-TZVPP// MP2/Def2-TZVPP
	AIE1 (AIE2) ^a	AIE1 (AIE2) ^a
<i>cis</i> - $[As_7H_4]$	6.47 (5.77)	6.10 (5.35)
<i>trans</i> - $[As_7H_4]$	5.72 (5.22)	5.40 (5.02)
<i>cis</i> - $[As_7Me_4]$	7.21 (4.63)	6.97 (4.51)
<i>trans</i> - $[As_7Me_4]$	5.81 (4.65)	5.48 (4.50)

^aAIE1 = E *cis/trans* isomer 2 cation – E *cis/trans* isomer 2 neutral; AIE2 = E *cis/trans* isomer 1 cation – E *cis/trans* isomer 1 neutral.

Fig. 2. Optimized geometries and their relative energies of neutral and cation *cis* and *trans* $[As_7Me_4]$ isomers.

Fig. 3. AdNDP 2c-2e results of stable neutral *cis*, *trans*-[As₇Me₄] isomer 2 with the occupation number.

as organo-Zintl superalkalis, we wanted to study the bonding features inside these clusters. The first thing we wanted to establish that the ligands are sharing their valence electron to form the bond with the core. For that, we have used adaptive natural density partitioning (AdNDP) technique to find a 2c-2e bond between As₇³⁻ and the ligand. We have generated only the 2c-2e bond for three positions where ligands are linked with As₇³⁻. The 2c-2e bonds with their occupation number (ON) of the *cis*, *trans*-[As₇Me₄] complexes are given in Fig. 3. The occupation number gives the information about the amount of charge sharing between the two centers. In the calculation of the 2c-2e bonds, the ON should be close to two. From Fig. 3, we see that there exists a 2c-2e sigma bond between Me and As₇ in [As₇Me₄] *cis* and *trans* isomers with an ON of 1.99 |e|. From this we confirm that the ligand Me ligands share one of its valence electron to form a 40-electronic [As₇Me₄] system. The 2c-2e bonds with their occupation numbers of the neutral *cis*, *trans*-[As₇H₄] are given in Supporting Information S14.

To know the bonding pattern in detail, we have generated the density of states (DOS) and partial density of states (PDOS) of the studied clusters to check the contribution of the core and ligand towards the frontier molecular orbitals. The corresponding plots of *cis*, *trans*-[As₇Me₄] along with the % contributions are shown in Fig. 4. We have found that, the contribution in the HOMO and the LUMO came from the core. However, ligand contribution is observed in the higher molecular orbitals like LUMO+6, LUMO+7, LUMO+8, etc. The plots of *cis*, *trans*-[As₇H₄] complexes along with the % contributions are given in Supporting Information S15.

Fig. 4. The calculated PDOS diagrams and contribution of the core and ligand towards FMO of *cis*, *trans*-[As₇Me₄]; red, black and blue colours indicate the As₇ core, the ligand Me and the total DOS, respectively.

(b) [Sb₇R₄] (R = H, Me) complexes:

The optimized geometries of neutral and cation [Sb₇Me₄] complexes with their relative energies are shown in Fig. 5 and the optimized geometries of neutral and cation [Sb₇H₄] complexes with their relative energies are given Supporting Information S16. From the relative energies, we can confirm that isomer 2 is more stable than isomer 1 in neutral *cis* and

Fig. 5. Optimized geometries and their relative energies of neutral and cation *cis* and *trans* $[Sb_7Me_4]$ isomer complexes.

trans isomers and in cation *cis* and *trans* isomers the isomer 1 is more stable. After knowing the stable optimized geometries of these complexes, we have calculated the adiabatic ionization energies of all the complexes. The calculated AIE's of $[Sb_7R_4]$ ($R = H, Me$) complexes are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Calculated adiabatic ionization energies of Sb_7R_4 ($R = H$ and Me) complexes at B3LYP and MP2 level of theories by using Def2-TZVPP basis set

Complexes	Adiabatic ionization energies (AIE's)	
	B3LYP/Def2-TZVPP	B3LYP/Def2-TZVPP// MP2/Def2-TZVPP
	AIE1 (AIE2) ^a	AIE1 (AIE2) ^a
<i>cis</i> - $[Sb_7H_4]$	6.19 (5.59)	6.10 (5.28)
<i>trans</i> - $[Sb_7H_4]$	5.90 (5.61)	5.64 (5.31)
<i>cis</i> - $[Sb_7Me_4]$	5.63 (5.11)	5.32 (4.83)
<i>trans</i> - $[Sb_7Me_4]$	5.41 (5.09)	5.09 (4.78)

^aAIE1 = $E_{cis/trans \text{ isomer 2 cation}} - E_{cis/trans \text{ isomer 2 neutral}}$; AIE2 = $E_{cis/trans \text{ isomer 1 cation}} - E_{cis/trans \text{ isomer 1 neutral}}$.

From the calculated AIE values, it is evident that the results are following same trend as we have seen in the case of As_7^{3-} . The *cis*, *trans*- $[Sb_7H_4]$ isomers do not make superalkali due to the fact that H has no electron donating ability while Me is electron donating group.

To find 2c-2e bond between Sb_7^{3-} and the ligands, we have used adaptive natural density partitioning (AdNDP) technique. The 2c-2e bonds with their occupation number (ON)

of the neutral *cis*, *trans*- $[Sb_7H_4]$ complexes are given in Supporting Information S17 and the *cis*, *trans*- $[Sb_7Me_4]$ complexes are given in Fig. 6. In the calculation of the 2c-2e bonds, the ON should be close to two. From Fig. 6, we have observed that there exists a 2c-2e sigma bond between Me and Sb_7 in $[Sb_7Me_4]$ with an ON of 1.99 |e|. By this evidence we can confirm that the Me ligands share one of its valance electron to form a $[Sb_7Me_4]$ which is a 40-electron system.

Density of states (DOS) and partial density of states (PDOS) for *cis*, *trans*- $[Sb_7Me_4]$ complexes along with the percentage contributions of core and ligands towards the frontier molecular orbitals are shown in Fig. 7. It follows a similar trend as we have seen in As complexes. The HOMO and the LUMO is mainly contributed by the Sb_7 core. The ligand contribution is found in the higher molecular orbitals like LUMO+6, LUMO+7, LUMO+8, etc. The DOS and PDOS for *cis*, *trans*- $[Sb_7H_4]$ are given in Supporting Information S18.

(c) $[Bi_7R_4]$ ($R = H, Me$) complexes:

In the similar way, we have optimized the molecular geometries for both the *cis*, *trans*- $[Bi_7R_4]$ complex. The optimized geometries of *cis*, *trans*- $[Bi_7Me_4]$ isomers along with the relative energy values are given in Fig. 8. The optimized geometries of neutral *cis*, *trans*- $[Be_7H_4]$ complexes with their relative energies are given in Supporting Information S19. From the calculated relative energies, we confirm that in neutral *cis* and *trans* isomers the isomer 2 is more stable than isomer 1. To know the ionization energy of these com-

Fig. 6. AdNDP 2c-2e results of stable neutral *cis*, *trans*-[Sb₇Me₄] isomer 2 with the occupation number.

Fig. 7. The calculated PDOS diagrams and contribution of the core and ligand towards FMO of *cis*, *trans*-[Sb₇Me₄]; red, black and blue colours indicate the Sb₇ core, the ligand Me and the total DOS, respectively.

plexes we have optimized the cation geometries of all the complexes. In cation *cis* and *trans* isomers, the isomer 1 is

more stable than isomer 2. From all the optimized geometries of these complexes, we have calculated the AIE. All

Fig. 8. Optimized geometries and their relative energies of neutral and cation *cis* and *trans* $[Bi_7Me_4]$ isomer complexes.

Table 3. Calculated adiabatic ionization energies of Bi_7R_4 ($R = H$ and Me) complexes at B3LYP and MP2 level of theories by using Def2-TZVPP basis set

Complexes	Adiabatic ionization energies (AIE's)	
	B3LYP/Def2-TZVPP	B3LYP/Def2-TZVPP// MP2/Def2-TZVPP
	AIE1 (AIE2) ^a	AIE1 (AIE2) ^a
<i>cis</i> - $[Bi_7H_4]$	5.74 (5.58)	5.25 (5.06)
<i>trans</i> - $[Bi_7H_4]$	5.98 (5.59)	5.06 (5.08)
<i>cis</i> - $[Bi_7Me_4]$	5.61 (5.15)	5.11 (4.66)
<i>trans</i> - $[Bi_7Me_4]$	5.78 (5.13)	4.91 (4.61)

^aAIE1 = $E_{cis/trans}$ isomer 2 cation – $E_{cis/trans}$ isomer 2 neutral; AIE2 = $E_{cis/trans}$ isomer 1 cation – $E_{cis/trans}$ isomer 1 neutral.

the calculated AIE values are given in Table 3.

In Table 3, except *cis*- $[Bi_7Me_4]$, *trans*- $[Bi_7Me_4]$ complexes, the rest of the complexes do not make superalkalis as their AIE's are higher than alkali metals as found in B3LYP/Def2-TZVPP level of theory calculation. But, MP2 calculations on the complexes reveal that they make superalkali as their AIE's are lower than alkali metals.

To know the electron sharing pattern, we have used AdNDP technique to find a 2c-2e bond between Bi_7^{3-} core and the ligands. The 2c-2e bonds with their occupation number (ON) of the neutral *cis*, *trans*- $[Bi_7Me_4]$ complexes are given in Fig. 9. The *cis*, *trans*- $[Bi_7H_4]$ 2c-2e bonds with their

Fig. 9. AdNDP 2c-2e results of stable neutral *cis*, *trans*- $[Bi_7Me_4]$ isomer 2 with the occupation number.

ON's are given in Supporting Information S20. In all these complexes the ON is close to two which suggests that ligands are sharing their valence electrons to make 40 electronic $[Bi_7R_4]$ complexes.

As done before for the As and Sb complexes, we have calculated the DOS and PDOS for $[Bi_7R_4]$ complexes to know the bonding pattern. From the Fig. 10 we have found that the contribution of the HOMO and LUMO and the ligand contribution are similar to the previous As and Sb complexes. The density of states (DOS) and partial density of states (PDOS) and the corresponding plots for *cis*, *trans*- $[Bi_7H_4]$ are given in Supporting Information S21.

Fig. 10. The calculated PDOS diagrams and contribution of the core and ligand towards FMO of *cis*, *trans*- $[Bi_7Me_4]$; black, red and blue colours indicate the Bi_7 core, the ligand Me and the total DOS, respectively.

Conclusions

From the above Results and discussion, we have found that all the group 15 Zintl ions X_7^{3-} ($X = As, Sb$ and Bi) can be able to make superalkali with suitable electron donating ligand. First principle calculation suggests that *trans* isomer is stable when the size of the ligand increases. Among all

the X_7^{3-} ($X = As, Sb$ and Bi) Zintl ions, As_7^{3-} is found to be the best candidate for making superalkali. The 2c-2e bonding pattern, DOS and PDOS explain the structural behaviour of the complexes and the pattern is similar for all the group 15 elements. H as ligand is not suitable for making superalkali as it has a very poor electron donating capacity. As we move from H to Me the adiabatic ionization energies are decreasing which tells that if we increase the electron donating capacity of ligand, a more efficient superalkali can be formed.

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Supporting information

The optimized geometries of all the complexes along with their Cartesian coordinates of *cis* and *trans* isomers are given in Supporting Information (SI) S1-S12. The relative energies, 2c-2e bonds and DOS, PDOS of X_7H_4 ($X = As, Sb$ and Bi) are shown in SI Figs. S13, S16, S19, Figs. S14, S17, S20 and Figs. S15, S18, S21.

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